

Participant Information Sheet

Project title: Socio-economic rehabilitation after quarrying

Project team: **Dr. Kamila Svobodova**, Principal Researcher, Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, University of Göttingen, Germany
Prof. Tobias Plieninger, Advisor and Chair of Social-Ecological Interactions in Agricultural Systems, Department of Agricultural Economics and Rural Development, University of Göttingen, Germany

What is the project about?

The project aims to determine effective socio-economic rehabilitation practices after quarrying (a surface mining producing industrial minerals and construction materials). By comparing different post-mining sites in three European countries – Germany, Denmark and Czech Republic, we investigate the relationships between the process of mine rehabilitation planning and the creation of social, economic and ecosystem benefits provided by the sites. In the Czech Republic, the project focuses on two quarrying regions – Tovačov and Suchdol nad Lužnicí.

How is the project being funded?

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 884761.

Why have I been asked to participate?

You have been nominated given your local knowledge of the region, the local communities, specialist expertise in quarrying practice in the region.

What will I need to do and how long will it take?

You are being asked to participate in an interview. The interview will be face-to-face. You will be interviewed by the Principal Researcher. The interview will take approximately 45 minutes. It will be recorded, and you will be asked about:

- (1) Your knowledge of the region.
- (2) Your relationship with the quarrying company and the communities.
- (3) Your perception of power and interest in the region.
- (4) Vision of what the region should look like in the future.
- (5) Concerns about the future of the region.

Is it compulsory to participate in this project?

No, participation is voluntary. You can choose to withdraw at any time. If you agree to participate in this project, you will be asked to provide your informed consent prior to your participation.

What will happen to the information I provide?

The interview will be recorded, and its highlights will be transcribed. Data collected in the interviews will be anonymized and stored on a secure, confidential, and password-protected site of the University of Göttingen. If you wish, we can send you the transcribed highlights for your review and you will have an opportunity to correct them.

The information you provide will help us to identify the relationships between the quarrying company and local communities.

The overall findings from the project will be published in scientific journals, presented at scientific conferences and public events, and promoted via the project websites <https://cesmine.com/> and social media. The results may be used in future projects conducted by the University of Göttingen.

Can I be identified as a result of participating in this project?

Your name will be known by the project team, but it will not be identified in any information that emerges from this work. Your personal information will not be shared with anyone external to the project. If you would like your contribution publicly acknowledged in the project report and associated research outputs, please advise the project team.

How will participants benefit from this project?

The benefits for the participants include the ability to influence the outcomes of the project by sharing their knowledge of living and/or working in quarrying regions. The project outcomes will be communicated to the representatives of the EU and national policies and to the quarrying companies. The outputs from this project will support decisions around mine rehabilitation and post-mining land use options to reflect socio-economic benefits provided by the site to affected communities.

For further information, please contact:

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Principal Researcher

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Informed Consent Form

Informed consent can be provided in a written or oral form – according to the participant's preferences.

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I agree to participate in this research project, and I acknowledge that:

- I have read and understood the information sheet provided.
- I agree to participate in the project.
- I understand that taking part in the project is voluntary and I can withdraw my participation at any time and without any consequences.
- I understand that my responses will be anonymized. I will not be named or possible to identified by outsiders in any of the project outputs, although my organization may be named.
- I agree with the interview being recorded on electronic devices.
- I am 18 years old and older.

Date	
Respondent's signature/ oral agreement	
Name	

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